

EFFECTS OF LAND USE CONFLICTS ON CROP OUTPUT OF RURAL HOUSEHOLDS IN BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to examine how land use conflicts affect crop productivity among rural households in Benue, Nigeria. For this study, one hundred and seventy (171) respondents were chosen using a three-stage selection approach. Semi-structured questionnaires were administered along with scheduled interviews to gather data. Both descriptive (frequency distribution, percentage, and mean) and inferential (multiple regression) statistics were applied to the data. The majority of respondents were men, with an average of 25 years of farming experience, according to the data. With an average family size of nine individuals and a majority (94.2%) having reasonable level of formal education. The respondents were full-time farmers. Moreover, 842% of the farmers reported having interaction with extension agents, and 80.7% reported belonging to a cooperative group. The majority of farmers (82.5%) have loans available to them. The three most common types of land use conflicts in the research area were those involving farmers and herders, border disputes, and ethnic conflicts inside communities. Farmers perceived that the main outcomes of land use disputes were low income for farmers ($X = 2.23$), poor crop output ($X = 4.29$), and disruption of family members' schooling ($X = 4.33$). The result of a multiple regression analysis showed that, at different probability levels, the following variables were significant to farmers' output: labor usage (-5.3204), fertilizer (11.7871), agro-chemical (-739.9539), age (-121.4139), farming experience (132.9224), extension contact (409.5729), frequency of attack (-507.3467), and migration (88.2148). The study finally recommends that farmers should adopt improved farming techniques and intensive cultivation by using improved seeds and farm inputs. Also, equitable distribution of resources and promotion of mutual respect for customs and traditional institutions by the government and authority concerned was recommended.

Keywords: Land use, Land use conflicts, Crop output

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is among the countries in the world with abundant natural resources. Nigeria occupies 923,773 square kilometers of land and has 216 million inhabitants, with a projected 2.7% annual population growth rate (National Population Commission (NPC), 2006; United Nations (UN), 2022). Nigeria has thus far benefited greatly from agricultural production, despite having only 42% of its 82,000 hectares of arable land under cultivation (NBS, 2016). For the majority of

rural households, agriculture continues to be the primary source of income, accounting for 58% of total family income and 42% coming from non-agricultural wage income (Olorunsanya *et al.*, 2013). The agriculture and agricultural-related sectors employ 60–70% of Nigeria's 197.8 million people, contributing 35–40% of GDP on average between 2008 and 2012 (Olorunsanya, *et al.*, 2014 and Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), 2013). It is sufficient to say that the nation has an abundance of water resources and fertile

terrain that can sustain the production of both food and cash crops.

Land is a precious resource that is extremely important for survival and development. It also generally contributes to the reduction of poverty in Africa and other regions of the world through agriculture, which is the primary source of income and employment for the majority of rural families. As a result, land continues to be Africa's primary source of development (Kironde, 2009). In the great majority of Africa, land is central to social, political, and economic life. The majority of Africans rely on farming and other land-based activities for their livelihoods, and land serves as the foundation for safe houses in both urban and rural areas (African Association (AU), 2006). Contending demands of land can however trigger conflicts particularly when the parcel of land is contested for belong to different group and interests (Wehrmann, 2008). The demand for land often times lead to clashes (Huggins, 2000). Prolonged conflicts and clashes have adverse consequences from various points of view; financial, social, spatial as well as agricultural development (Albert, 2003).

Conflicts over land are becoming more and more dangerous for rural economic activities such as farming in Nigeria and much of Sub-Saharan Africa (Yamano *et al.*, 2005; Deininger *et al.*, 2006). Conflicts over land lead to vulnerability and impede land development, which results in low agricultural yield per hectare (Deininger *et al.*, 2006). Despite its effect on agricultural development, small-scale conflicts have the potential to escalate into widespread disputes that could jeopardize public safety. In the light of the above, this study was conducted to determine how land use conflicts affected the lives of rural families in Benue State, Nigeria. the specific objectives were to: (i) determine the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers in the study area; (ii) determine the types of land use conflicts in the study area; (iii) evaluate the perceived effects of land use conflicts by the farmers in the study area, and (iv) examine the effects of land use conflicts on output of farmers in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Benue State, Nigeria. The State is located in the lower Benue River in the North- Central, Nigeria. The location of the state capital is Makurdi. Benue State has a population density of 137 persons per square kilometer and a land area of approximately 31,276.7 square kilometers. The State's diverse land holdings have earned it the nickname "Food Basket" of the nation. The state is situated between longitudes 6o 35' and 10o 28' east of the equator and scope 6o 30' and 8o 10' north (Benue State Horticultural and Rustic Improvement Authority (BNARDA), 2014). With 4,219,244 residents, the state has 23 Neighborhood Government Regions (LGAs) (Public Populace Commission, 2006). However, based on Nigeria's 2.3% annual population growth rate (Public Department of Measurements, 2023), the State's expanded population as of 2022 was 6,070,784 people. The state imposes boundaries on five distinct states: Kogi State to the west, Enugu and Ebonyi States to the south-west, Cross-Waterway to the east, Nasarawa to the north, and Taraba to the east. Additionally, the State and the Republic of Cameroun share a common global boundary in the southeast (Benue State Government (BSG), 2015).

Sampling Procedures and Sample size

For the study, a three-stage sampling procedure was adopted. Stage one involved purposive selection of three LGAs in the State with frequent occurrences of land use conflicts from the three agricultural development project zones in the State. The next stage involved proportionate selection by 10% of the villages in each of the LGAs, giving a total of 16 villages (6+6+4=16). The third and final step involved selecting a total of 171 respondents using Yamane's formula (1967). The Yamane (1967) equation for appropriate example size assurance as applied by Eboh (2009) and Ibrahim (2016) is as follow.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(-e)^2}$$

(1)

Where;

n = samples size

N = finite population

e = limit of tolerable error (level of precision at 0.07)

l = constant

Data Collection and Analysis

The research employed primary data collected through the administration of a structured questionnaire, accompanied by an interview schedule. To ensure content validity of the data collection instrument, expert consultations were carried out. Analysis of the gathered data involved descriptive methods like frequency count and percentages, as well as inferential

statistics such as multiple regression analysis. Descriptive statistics were applied to achieve Objectives i, ii, and iii. The perceived effects of respondents on land use conflicts were measured using a 5-point Likert rating scale, while Objective iv was accomplished through a multiple regression model. The model is implicitly specified as:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, X_9, X_{10}, X_{11}, X_{12}, X_{13}, X_{14}, X_{15}, X_{16}, X_{17}) \quad (2)$$

The multiple regression models' explicit functional forms were as follows:

Linear:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + u_i \quad (3)$$

Cobb-Douglas:

$$\ln Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + \dots + \beta_n \ln X_n + U_i \quad (4)$$

Semi-log:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + \dots + \beta_n \ln X_n + U_i \quad (5)$$

Exponential:

$$\ln Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + U_i \quad (6)$$

Where:

Y = Crop output of the respondents (measured using grain weight equivalent in kg)

X₁ = Farm size (hectare)

X₂ = Labour usage (mandays)

X₃ = Planting materials (kg)

X₄ = Fertilizer (kg)

X₅ = Agro-chemicals (liters)

- X_6 = Age (years)
 X_7 = Household size (number)
 X_8 = Education (years)
 X_9 = Farming experience (years)
 X_{10} = Annual income (Naira)
 X_{11} = Extension contact (number)
 X_{12} = Cooperative membership (years)
 X_{13} = Land use conflict (number)
 X_{14} = Frequency of conflicts (number of occurrence)
 X_{15} = Migration (Dummy variable; 1 if migrated, 0 if otherwise)
 X_{16} = Loss of lives (number)
 X_{17} = Loss of animals (number)

β_0 = constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_{17}$ = coefficients of the independent variables

$X_1 - X_{17}$ = independent variables

u_i = error term

ln = natural log

RESULTS

Socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers

Table 1 revealed that significant proportions (80.9%) of farmers in the study area are within the age bracket of 31-50 years, with a mean age of 42 years. This indicates a substantial involvement of the youth in farming activities in the research location, consistent with findings by Manu *et al.* (2014) and Adelokun *et al.* (2015), who observed a similar age distribution in conflict-prone agricultural regions. Additionally, the majority (85.4%) of respondents were male, while 14.6% were female, suggesting a predominant male presence in farming, possibly due to women being more engaged in domestic responsibilities. This aligns with Achike's (2002) observation that men face fewer

constraints in agricultural activities compared to women.

Moreover, Table 1 indicates that a significant portion (94.2%) of farmers possessed some form of formal education, with an average of 11 years in formal schooling. About 66.5% of farmers had farming experience ranging from 11 to 30 years, with an average farming experience of 25 years. The average household size of respondents was 9 persons. Additionally, the majority (78.9%) considered agriculture as their primary occupation, while 21.1% were involved in alternative occupations such as trading, artisan work, or civil service. This finding resonates with Adisa *et al.* (2010) and Ogunmefun *et al.* (2015), who reported that farming serves as the main occupation in conflict affected areas, and alternative occupations are pursued to supplement household income.

Table 1: Distribution of the farmers according to socio-economic characteristics

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age			
<30	27	15.8	
31-40	51	29.7	
41-50	62	36.3	
51-60	22	12.9	
>60	9	5.3	42
Sex			
Male	146	85.4	
Female	25	14.6	
Marital status			
Single	11	6.4	
Married	140	81.9	
Divorced	8	4.7	
Widowed	7	4.1	
Separated	5	2.9	
Educational attainment			
No formal education	10	5.8	
Primary	42	24.6	
Secondary	72	42.1	
ND/NCE	25	14.6	
HND/Degree	22	12.9	11
Farming experience			
< 10	16	9.4	
11- 20	61	35.7	
21-30	51	29.8	
> 30	43	25.1	25
Household size			
< 6	29	17.0	
6-10	82	48.0	
11-15	48	28.1	
16-20	11	6.3	
> 20	1	0.6	9
Primary occupation			
Farming	135	78.9	
Trading	26	15.2	
Civil servant	7	4.1	
Artisans	3	1.8	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Institutional variables accessed by the farmers

The institutional variables accessed by the farmers in the study region were displayed in Table 2's results. It was found that while 15.8% of farmers did not have contact with extension agents, the majority of farmers (84.2%) had contact with extension agents. Furthermore,

33.3% of farmers reported having quarterly interactions with extension agents. This finding is consistent with Kimenyi *et al.* (2014) and Robertson *et al.* (2012), who found that most extension contacts with farmer groups and other resource users occurred on a quarterly basis.

Table 2: Distribution according to institutional variables accessed by the farmers

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Extension contact		
No	27	15.8
Yes	144	84.2
Frequency of contact		
None	27	15.8
Weekly	9	5.3
Forth-nightly	28	16.3
Monthly	36	21.1
Quarterly	57	33.3
Annually	14	8.2
Membership of cooperative		
No	33	19.3
Yes	138	80.7
Access to credit		
No	30	17.5
Yes	141	82.5
Sources of credit		
Commercial Bank	2	1.2
Agricultural Bank	30	17.5
Microfinance Bank	6	3.5
Cooperative society	66	38.6
Money lender	15	8.8
Family member/relation	52	30.4
Amount of credit accessed		
50,000- 150,000	101	59.1
151,000-250,000	12	7.0
251,000-350,000	37	21.6
351,000-500,000	21	12.3

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Additionally, Tables 2 revealed a significant proportion (80.7%) of farmers were registered members of various cooperative groups. Membership in such associations provides farmers with opportunities to access financial institutions and lending agencies, as these requirements often act as determining factors. This aligns with the findings of Odebiyi (2010) and Abdulazeez (2015), who reported the cooperative's role in ensuring that members derive collective benefits they might not obtain individually. Aniedu (2016) also supports this, emphasizing that cooperative societies offer advantages such as access to micro-credit and resource inputs at a reduced cost, contributing to increased crop output for rural households. Furthermore, Table 2 indicates that a majority (82.5%) of farmers had access to credit. This finding is consistent with Olorunsanya (2013) observation that rural farming households require credit for investment, and such funding often comes in the form of grants, gifts, or loans due to their limited capital base. Notably, 38.6% of respondents obtained credit from cooperative societies, while 30.4% sourced credit from friends and relatives. This suggests

that cooperative membership facilitates access to credit for farming activities. However, the majority (59.1%) of farmers accessed credit within the range of ₦50,000 – ₦150,000, indicating that most farmers in the study area operated as small-scale farmers with a focus on subsistence farming.

Types of land use conflicts experienced by the farmers

The results of types of land use conflicts experienced by respondents in the study area presented in Table 3 revealed that pastoralists and farmers (65.5%) ranked first. This was followed by in second place boundary conflicts (63.2%) and ethno-communal (42.1%) ranked third. This finding implies that the most prevalent land use conflict in the State was that between farmers and pastoralists. This result is consistent with findings by Olayoku (2014), Mercy Corps (2015) and Adeoye (2017), who stated that herders-farmers conflicts remain the most preponderant conflict in the North-Central Nigeria hinged on land resource control which has been heightened by pressure on land conflict actors, and the absence or lack of clarity of land use boundaries.

Table 3: Types of land use conflicts experienced by the farmers

Variable	Frequency*	Percentage	Rank
Pastoralists-farmers conflicts	112	65.5	1 st
Boundary conflicts	108	63.2	2 nd
Ethno-communal conflicts	72	42.1	3 rd
Inter-group conflicts	71	41.5	4 th
Family conflicts over land	51	29.8	5 th
Farmer-farmer conflicts	49	28.7	6 th
Farmer-fisher folk conflicts	8	4.7	7 th
Herders-fisher folks conflicts	4	2.3	8 th

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Note: * implies multiple responses

Perceived effects of land use conflicts on output and income of the farmers

Farmers in the study area agreed with all the perception statements on the effects of land use conflicts on output and income as shown in Table 4. The leading perception statement of effects of land use conflict by the farmers were; It disrupts of education family members ($X = 4.39$), It results in poor crop production ($X = 4.37$), It results in low income for farmers ($X = 4.30$) and it brings about insecurity ($X = 4.29$)

which ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th, respectively. This result is consistent with that of Agbi (2013), who stated that conflict is a basic and necessary aspect of life since people are bound to have competitive interest when interacting with one another. The finding is in line with the finding of Ekong (2003) who reported that internal violence and conflicts over resource use in some countries has caused large number of rural people to seek comparative safety of the cities of their respective society.

Table 4: Distribution of farmers based on perceived effects of land use conflicts

Perception Statements	Weighted sum	Weighted Mean	Rank	Remark
Disrupts education of family members	750	4.39	1 st	A
Results in poor crop production	748	4.37	2 th	A
Brings about insecurity	735	4.30	3 rd	A
Results in low income for farmers	733	4.29	4 th	A
Leads to social disturbance	726	4.25	5 th	A
Results in food insecurity	719	4.20	6 th	A
Results in rural-urban migration	705	4.12	7 th	A
Leads to loss of family members	689	4.03	8 th	A
Creates unemployment	681	3.98	9 th	A
Brings about poverty	673	3.94	10 th	A
Leads to abandonment of farming	614	3.59	11 th	A
Brings about urban congestion	561	3.28	12 th	A

Source: Field survey, 2019

Note: A = Agreed

Effects of land use conflicts on farmers' output

The results from the multiple regression analysis on the effects of land use conflicts on farmers' output presented in Table 5 showed R^2 value of 0.9033 suggests that approximately 90% of the variation in farmers' output is explained by the predictor variables in the model, leaving around 10% unaccounted for, likely due to estimation errors. The F-statistic value of 84.05, significant at the 1% level of probability, indicates the model's goodness of fit.

The coefficient of labor usage (-5.3204) is

negative and significant at the 5% level, suggesting that employing additional labor leads to a decrease in output. This may be attributed to farmers relying more on unpaid (family) labor than hired labor, potentially resulting in less supervision and efficiency on the farm. This finding aligns with Aniedu (2016) who reported that the use of unskilled (family) labor can decrease farmers' output in North Central Nigeria.

The coefficient of fertilizer usage (-11.7871) is negative and significant at the 1% level, indicating that an increase in fertilizer application is associated with reduced output.

This contradicts Asiyanbola's (2008) findings of a positive relationship between fertilizer application and farmer output in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Similarly, the coefficient of agro-chemical (-739.9539) is negative and significant at the 1% level, suggesting that the application of agro-chemicals could reduce farmers' output, possibly due to excessive and toxic application.

The coefficient of age (-121.4139) is negative and significant at the 1% level, implying that as farmers age, their output tends to decrease. This could be attributed to a decline in strength compared to young and highly productive farmers. On the other hand, the coefficient of experience in farming (132.9224) is positive and significant at the 1% level, indicating that an increase in experience leads to better output,

likely due to practical knowledge and skills acquired over time. This finding is consistent with Aniedu (2016), who stated that farming experience has a positive and significant effect on farmers' output in North Central Nigeria.

The coefficient of extension contact (409.5729) is positive and significant at the 1% level, suggesting that access to extension services contributes to better output. This aligns with the findings of Birhan *et al.* (2017), who reported that access to extension and advisory services, enhances rural farmers' output. Lastly, the coefficient of the frequency of attacks (-507.3467) is negative and significant at the 5% level, indicating that continuous attacks result in a reduction in farmers' output.

Table 5: Regression estimate on effects of land use conflicts on farmers' output

Variables	Coefficients	Standard error	t-value
Farm size	319.9917	215.8656	1.48
Labour usage	-5.3204	2.3396	-2.27**
Planting material	-18.8556	266.7532	-0.07
Fertilizer	-11.7871	1.1360	-10.38***
Agro-chemicals	-739.9539	237.381	-3.12***
Age	-121.4139	46.1690	-2.63***
Household size	-25.0771	107.3136	-0.23
Education	-23.1650	66.3368	-0.35
Farming exp.	132.9224	50.1540	2.63***
Annual income	0.0004	0.0007	0.68
Extension contact	409.5729	112.3865	3.64***
Membership of coop.	-343.0878	621.1831	-0.55
Land use conflict	197.3723	186.1992	1.06
Frequency of attack	-507.3467	217.3593	-2.33**
Migration	162.7762	113.4367	1.43
Loss of animal	95.2979	167.6801	0.57
Loss of lives	-203.783	265.4307	0.77
Constant	-5199.282	1784.766	-2.91***
R-square	0.9033		
Adjusted R-square	0.8925		
F- Statistics	84.05***		

Sources: Field survey, 2019

Note: *** and ** implies significant at 1% and 5% level of probability, respectively.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusively, majority of crop farmers in the study area were men and many of them were married. The majorities of farmers were full-time farmers, had large households, and had some form of formal education. The study further found that majority of the farmers had extension contact, were members of cooperative society and had access to credit. The majority of the farmers owned land acquired mostly through inheritance, and exceeding three hectares. The most common land use dispute was between farmers and pastoralist. The effects of land use disputes on farmers' yield revealed that, while farming experience and extension contact had

beneficial effects on output, labor, frequency of attack, fertilizer usage, agrochemicals, and age had negative effects. The necessity of implementing better farming practices was suggested in light of the study conclusion. By employing improved seeds and agricultural inputs, farmers should switch to intensive farming practices. Also, access to credit facilities should be targeted at rural farmers who have lost significant members of their household as a result of land use conflicts. This will help in attracting the migrant youths back to the rural areas as they will now have less incentive to stay in the cities.

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